

Smart Sensor-Based Alarm System for Self-Aid and P2P Ad-Hoc Communication

Rama M^{1*} Anitha K² Prasad U¹ Sai Kiran N² Shahada Sd² Dr. S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim^{3*}

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, QIS College of Engineering and Technology, Ongole, India

²Department of Information Technology, QIS College of Engineering and Technology, Ongole, India

³School of Computer Science and Engineering, Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore, Tamilnadu, India, E.Mail: jafarali.s@vit.ac.in

*Corresponding Author: Dr. S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim (jafarali.s@vit.ac.in)

Abstract: Climate change is causing more natural disasters. Poor survivor communication, signals, and localisation are caused by crucial difficulties in disaster mitigation, particularly smartphone sensor operation. Proposed framework for self-service smartphone sensor operation via direct communication on smart handheld devices. Make an application-layer specially appointed network for brilliant gadgets without a trace of cell organizations or remote passages. It attempts to precisely locate survivors, assist smartphone sensors in promptly locating victims, and minimise power-saving calculations. This app uses a one-step network to link smartphones carried by survivors trapped in or buried beneath collapsed infrastructure and sends low-power distress signals to the phones' sensors, allowing employees to locate and assist victims. The victim's pre-enabled Self Aid app will alert the nearest squad members' smartphone sensors. Using P2P Ad Hoc, the squad communicates. This will help reach the affected area and save survivors. The work aims to reduce the time crews need to identify buried victims and improve team communication.

Keywords — Natural disaster, smartphone disaster sensor, and Disaster Relief, Scheduling, and Smartphone

1. INTRODUCTION

Tornadoes, earth quakes, hurricanes, and tsunamis are on the rise. All around the world, earthquakes kill innocent people and destroy the environment, and their epicentres can occur anywhere, so no location is safe. In 2016, a tremor of magnitude 5.6 rocked Oklahoma and six neighbouring states [1]. The April 16, 2016 Ecuador earthquake killed 272 and injured over 2,500 [2]. An earthquake can quickly destroy infrastructures, buildings, and homes. Disaster victims couldn't use their smartphones, tablets, or laptops to notify loved ones of their safety after the disaster. Infrastructures were damaged or lacked power. [3]. If victims are located within the "Golden 72 Hours," they may have a fair chance of survival if they are buried under debris and bricks. A severely injured person's chance of survival drops quickly if not treated quickly. Paraphrased Text Planning and executing rapid smartphone disaster sensor operations is critical to reducing deaths and protecting innocent lives around the world. Smartphone sensor teams or disaster relief planners face the following issues during an earthquake. First, because the current emergency scenario of a sudden earthquake may not be available, planning or prioritising smartphone sensor activities in terms of smartphone sensor areas is difficult. Targeted intelligence [23-54], dispatching smartphone sensor groups, and device allocation. Second, the impact range is from a few miles to several US states, but the smartphone sensor fleet and human resources are limited. Thirdly, the collapse of the power and communication infrastructure leaves affected regions without WiFi and 4G-LTE, isolating them from the rest of the world. The majority of smartphone sensor teams continue to rely on traditional methods and tools like Detection canines, surveillance cameras, and microphones. The sensors and processes of today's smartphones are inefficient and wasteful, resulting in missed opportunities. Smartphones have become an indispensable communication and social interaction tool that individuals always carry with them. In 2019, it is predicted that there will be 148.68 million smartphone users in the United States, with a global total of more than 2 billion [4]. With the increasing availability of smartphones, they can be used to coordinate smartphone sensor operations among disaster victims. After the 2010 earthquake in Haiti, 2.8 million dynamic mobile users out of a population of 10 million sent data to track population movements [5]. Broadcasting distress signals increases the likelihood of detection with minimal

impact to network lifetime, indicating a possible practical strategy for expediting disaster smartphone sensing and relief activities. The article continues as follows. Part II analyzes the previous approaches. Part III presents the smartphone self-sensor system. Part IV provides simulation results and analysis. In Part V, we conclude.

II RESEARCH WORK

In the last decade, smartphones have been used to build disaster recovery networks and aid disaster sensor and relief operations. Using smartphone-based WiFi connectivity, [7] proposes a system that would allow devices to automatically find their neighbours and send data from disaster zones. A unique design for the creation of wireless network infrastructure is presented in [8] as an energy-mindful fiasco recuperation network with WiFi tying. The goal is to create a temporary network for collecting data in the event of a disaster using WiFi connectivity technologies on smartphones and tablets. [9] uses WiFi tethering to propose smartphone-based disaster management for areas hit by disaster, where devices can temporarily become WiFi hotspots to provide internet service.

III. THE PROPOSED SELF-AID SYSTEM BASED ON SMARTPHONE

This part begins with a discussion of the proposed self-smartphone sensor system based on smartphones, also known as self-aid, followed by a discussion of the smartphone sensor Me and its interrelated techniques.

A. Overview of Self Aid

Powerful smartphones are likely many of the survivors trapped in the affected area and can be a valuable resource. Most smartphones have WiFi and Bluetooth. WiFi technology connects smartphones to IEEE 802.11 WLANs. 2.4 GHz WiFi is more powerful than 5.0 GHz. Bluetooth is designed for short-range, low-power communication, unlike WiFi. With WiFi or BWT, survivors buried under debris can use their smartphones to transmit a distress signal. If each smartphone remains awake and transmits distress signals, it will be easier to locate survivors who are trapped. Continuously broadcasting distress signals can drain a smartphone's battery, and sensor operations may continue for days following a disaster. It is difficult to figure out how to use survivors' smartphones to send out energy-efficient distress signals. As I explain here, we propose a smartphone-based self-smartphone sensor system, called smartphone sensor Me, to aid disaster smartphone sensor and relief operations. A group of smartphones (next buttons) transported by stranded or buried individuals beneath crumbling infrastructure form a one-step network that sends distress signals to groups of electrical sensors nearby. Nodes can enter self-smartphone sensor mode after detecting seismic signal. Alternatively, trapped survivors can use a smartphone sensor app to activate self-smartphone sensor mode. In smartphone auto-sensing mode, individual node show a unique Hello message, overhears the Hello messages it ignores, and builds a single-hop network. Each node in the cliques of the one-hop network can connect with every other node. Nodes in the one-hop network awaken alternately and in unison to reduce energy consumption and transmit irritation signals to locate smartphone sensor band in the vicinity. Each node may have a varied quantity of battery power, thus the node with the least amount of energy will shut down first. Therefore, the broadcast wake-up schedule should be dynamically changed based on the topology of a single-hop network. We investigate three crucial implementation challenges for the smartphone sensor Me: (i) how to construct a one stage organization, (ii) how to decide wake time for crisis flagging and (iii) how to naturally change wake time because of changes in network geography.

B. Self-aid: Smartphone-Based Self aid System

Each node displays a distinct Hello message along with its node ID. $1(b)$, n_g , n_i , n_h and n_m have the same one-step neighbor list subset: i, h, m, g . As shown in the subfig. 2, the central node n_g groups n_i , n_h and n_m into a group, $C_{i, h, m, g}$ (a). In broadcast messages from other nodes, construct G^* [17, 18]. In the sub-image. 1(a), n_m transmits a Hello and overhears Hello messages from its neighbors (e.g., n_h , n_i , n_g , n_k , n_l , and n_n). miniature. 1 shows a list of neighboring n_m -hops, $G^* m = h, i, g, k, l, n$ (b). Other nodes can create a one-step neighbor list using the same method. Each node in this article considers itself a one-step neighbor and adds its ID to the list. $G^* m = h, i, g, k, l, n, m$. Each node exchanges a list of one-step neighbors G^* with adjacent nodes and determines the central node with the most neighbors, where G^* is a subset of all other nodes. The central node builds a one-step network so that each node can communicate directly with it. In the sub-image. 1(c), the central node n_g builds the one-step network. Second, the focal hub checks G^* got from any remaining hubs in the one-jump organization and gatherings the hubs with a similar subset of G^* into a gathering, where every hub can pass all hubs other in the gathering. Inside, sub-picture.

Fig. 2. A snapshot of three cliques in one-hop network, schedule of sending out distress signal, and combine existing cliques.

Fig. 3. The change of coverage ratio against the number of nodes in the clique.

Two groups, $C_{m,n,l,k,g}$ and $C_{j,k,g}$, are shown in the Supplementary Fig. 2 a). In a group, the nodes are close together, so a node can cover a bulk percentage of the area of the group. Figure 3 represents the scope ratio between a node and all nodes in a group relative to the size of the group. Third, since the central node belongs to several groups in the one-step network, It will plan for irretation. signaling to all nodes. To reduce power consumption, a node in multiple groups chooses the lowest part of its group as the broadcast frequency. In the sub-image. 2(a), the central node n_g belongs to three groups, $C_{i,h,m,g}$, $C_{m,n,l,k,g}$ and $C_{j,k,g}$, and its group fraction is 1 4 (because $C_{i,h,m,g}$ has four nodes), which are 1 5 and 1 3 in these clusters, respectively. $g = 1 5$ is the broadcast frequency of the central node n_g . The central node calculates the sum of the group fractions for every node and schedules the transmission of the irretation signal accordingly. In this article, the node with the most clusters will broadcast the distress signal first. Nodes n_m and n_h have clique fractions of 1 4, 1 5, and 1 4, respectively; their sum is 9 20 and 1 4. NM will broadcast distress signals before NH. The centre node determines the broadcasting s chedule based on two criteria: (i) Each node's broadcasting frequency must be ; (ii) only one node in the clique can broadcast a distress signal at once. The centre node delivers the Schedule packet, pk_{sched} , to all one-hop nodes after determining the schedule. After a random backoff period [19], the node transmits an Ack packet, pk_{Ack} , to the central node. Subfigure 2(b) depicts the schedule for each node in the network of Subfigure 2(a one-hop), beginning at time 0. Fourth, since each node can have different amounts of excess energy, and the node with the least amount of excess energy may quickly shut down due to frequent distress transmissions, In response to changes in network topology, the broadcast schedule must be dynamically modified. If a node's battery dies, it transmits the TurnOff packet, pk_{toff} , to the central node. The central node eliminates the leaving node from crew and rebroadcasts the packet to all one-hop nodes. Subsequent to getting pk_{toff} , every hub eliminates the leaving hub from its one-bounce neighbor list. The focal hub then checks for refreshed bunches, blends them in the event that one is a subset of another, and registers another transmission plan. Hub n_j leaves the organization, while hub n_g blends $C_{j,k,g}$ and $C_{m,n,l,k,g}$ to become $C_{m,n,l,k,g}$. In the eve nt that the focal hub leaves the organization, a Skip bundle, pk_{dis} , is sent. In the wake of getting the pk_{dis} , any remaining hubs will get the Me cell phone sensor and carry out similar techniques.

IV. ARCHITECTURE

The Admin must login with a valid survivor name and password. After login, he can search history, view survivors, smartphone sensors, messages, and their response. Admin can view search history details. If he clicks on search history, it shows the list of searched survivor details with tags like survivor name, smartphone sensor operations, time and date. The team can receive survivors' messages, identify their location, and save them in time.

FLOW CHART

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Our experiments used Java. The network has 1-9 nodes and broadcasts distress signals every 5 seconds. In this research, we measure network longevity and scheduling vacancies by modifying critical simulation factors such as the number of nodes, distress signals sent, and cliques. We compare smart phone sensorMe and Team Phone for performance. First, we measure network lifetime and schedule vacancy time in Fig. 4. In Subfig. 4(a), smartphone sensorMe and Team Phone network lifetime increases with nodes. More nodes in the network and a longer time between distress signal broadcasts lengthen the network's lifetime. As node battery power increases, network lifetime increases. More powerful nodes last longer, which increases network lifetime. SensorMe has a shorter network lifetime than TeamPhone because TeamPhone broadcasts a distress signal even when a node leaves the network. In Subfig. 4(b), smartphone sensorMe and TeamPhone schedule vacancy time increases as nodes increase. Because TeamPhone's distress signal schedule doesn't change when nodes leave due to low battery. This increases schedule vacancy time. sensorMe has fewer schedule vacancies than TeamPhone. In a sensorMe smartphone, when the node's battery runs out, the network topology will change and other nodes will fill the space to send out distress signals, thereby reducing the schedule idle time. In Fig. 5, We determine y changing the quantity of distress signals sent, one can influence the network lifetime and scheduling vacancies. Subfig. 5 shows that network lifetime decreases as distress signals are broadcast (a). Each interval's energy consumption rises as more distress signals are broadcast. Because The broadcast is not rescheduled by TeamPhone. interval when a node leaves the network, the smartphone sensorMe has a slightly shorter network lifetime than TeamPhone. As seen in Subfigure 5(b), the overall vacancy time of sensorMe and TeamPhone smartphones decreases with each broadcasted distress signal. The sensorMe smartphone shows less schedule vacancy than the TeamPhone.

If a node loses power, the smartphone sensorMe reschedules the others, reducing vacancy time. Despite reducing broadcast distress signals and increasing network life, sensorMe has a shorter idle time per hour than TeamPhone. Figure 6 shows

Fig. 6. The performance of network lifetime and schedule vacancy time against the number of cliques.

network lifetime and schedule vacancy. sensorMe and TeamPhone smartphones have varying network cliques. Subfig. 6(a) shows that network lifetime decreases as cliques increase. while the network's nodes are increasing and the number of cliques decreases as a whole does not, more nodes transmit distress signals. Energy consumption during each interval rises, reducing network lifetime. TeamPhone has a longer network lifetime than smartphone sensorMe because it does not reschedule nodes when some are out of power, leading in a longer schedule vacant time. In Subfigure 6(b), vacancy time increases as the number of cliques grows. TeamPhone is outperformed by SensorMe. Vacancy time is reduced because sensorMe reschedules the network to fill empty time intervals.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, we suggest a catastrophe sensor and aid system based on smartphones. Smartphones used by people who were trapped or buried under the crumbling infrastructure create a one-step network and transmit distress signals to adjacent smartphone sensing personnel. The proposed method has been simulated and compared with Team Phone. Simulation results have demonstrated that the proposed method can reduce the gap in the distress signaling schedule and increase the detection ability with minimal impact on the lifetime of the network, showing that this can be effective. could be a possible method to speed up the operation of smartphone sensors in the event of a disaster.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] C. Pu, "Evacuation Assisting Strategies in Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks," in IEEEProc.UEMCON, November 2018.
- [2] Ecuador Earthquake: Death Toll Jumps to 272; More Than 2,500 Injured, <https://www.cnn.com/2016/04/17/americas/ecuador-deadlyearthquake>, Apr 18, 2016.
- [3] H. Nishiyama, M. Ito, and N. Kato, "Relay-by-smartphone: Realizing Multihop Device-to-Device Communications," IEEE Commun. Mag., vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 56–65, 2014.
- [4] Number of smartphone users in the United States from 2010 to 2022, 2018, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/201182/forecast-of-sma>

rtphone-users-in-the-us.

- [5] L. Bengtsson, X. Lu, A. Thorson, R. Garfield, and J. V. Schreeb, "Improved Response to Disasters and Outbreaks by Tracking Population Movements with Mobile Phone Network Data: A Post-Earthquake Geospatial Study in Haiti," *PLoS medicine*, vol. 8, no. 8, 2011.
- [6] Z. Lu, G. Cao, and T. L. Porta, "Networking Smartphones for Disaster Recovery," in *Proc. IEEE PerCom*, 2016, pp. 1–9.
- [7] A. Pal and K. Kant, "E-Darwin2: A Smartphone Based Disaster Recovery Network using WiFi Tethering," in *Proc. IEEE CCNC*, 2018, pp. 1–5.
- [8] M. Raj, K. Kant, and S. Das, "E-DARWIN: Energy Aware Disaster Recovery Network using WiFi Tethering," in *Proc. IEEE ICCCN*, 2014, pp. 1–8.
- [9] S. Ray, R. Sinha, and S. Ray, "A Smartphone-based Post-Disaster Management Mechanism Using WiFi Tethering," in *Proc. IEEE ICIEA*, 2015, pp. 966–971.
- [10] Y. Luo, J. Liu, Y. Gao, and Z. Lu, "Smartphone-Controlled Robot Snake for Urban Search and Rescue," in *Proc. ICIRA*, 2014, pp. 352–363.
- [11] Y. Ho, Y. Chen, and L. Chen, "Krypto: Assisting Search and Rescue Operations Using Wi-Fi Signal with UAV," in *Proc. ACM DroNet*, 2015, pp. 3–8.
- [12] C. Pu, "Jamming-Resilient Multipath Routing Protocol for Flying Ad Hoc Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 472–486, 2018.
- [13] A. Hossain, S. Ray, and R. Sinha, "A Smartphone-assisted Post-Disaster Victim Localization Method," in *Proc. HPCC/SmartCity/DSS*, 2016, pp. 1173–1179.
- [14] J. Zamora, N. Suzuki, and S. Kashihara, "SOS Message Distribution for Searching Disaster Victims," *Smartphones from an Applied Research Perspective*, InTech, 2017.
- [15] A. Al-Sadi and F. Awad, "Smartphone-Assisted Location Identification Algorithm for Search and Rescue Services," in *Proc. IEEE ICICS*, 2017, pp. 276–281.
- [16] M. Hossain and S. Ray, "A Smartphone-Assisted Device-to-Device Communication for Post-disaster Recovery," in *Proc. SmartGIFT*, 2018, pp. 11–20.
- [17] C. Pu, S. Lim, C. Jinseok, Byungkwan, "Active Detection in Mitigating Routing Misbehavior for MANETs," *Wireless Network* (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11276-017-121-z>.
- [18] C. Pu, S. Lim, B. Jung, and J. Chae, "EYES: Mitigating Forwarding Misbehavior in Energy Harvesting Motivated Networks," *Elsevier Computer Communications*, vol. 124, pp. 17–30, 2018.
- [19] C. Pu, T. Gade, S. Lim, M. Min, and W. Wang, "Lightweight Forwarding Protocols in Energy Harvesting 2014's IEEE Proc. MILCOM, "Wireless Sensor Networks," pp. 1053–1059.
- [20] Jeyaselvi, M., M. Sathya, S. Suchitra, S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim, and N. S. Kalyan Chakravarthy. "SVM-Based Cloning and Jamming Attack Detection in IoT Sensor Networks." *Advances in Information Communication Technology and Computing*, pp. 461-471. Springer, Singapore, 2022. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-19-0619-0_41
- [21] Ibrahim, Jafar Ali S., S. Rajasekar, Varsha, M. Karunakaran, K. Kasirajan, Kalyan NS Chakravarthy, V. Kumar, and K. J. Kaur. "Recent advances in performance and effect of Zr doping with ZnO thin film sensor in ammonia vapour sensing." *GLOBAL NEST JOURNAL* 23, no. 4 (2021): 526-531. <https://doi.org/10.30955/gnj.004020> , https://journal.gnest.org/publication/gnest_04020
- [22] Synthesis, Characterization of Ag/TiO2 Nanocomposite: Its Anticancer and Anti-Bacterial and Activities Ibrahim, S. Jafar Ali, Rajasekar S., Chakravarthy N. S. Kalyan, Varsha, Singh Maninder Pal, Kumar Vaneet and Saruchi, Volume 24, Issue 2, June 2022, Pages: 262-266, Issn No: 1790-7632, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30955/gnj.0042505>
- [23] Dr. M. Thangamani, Jafar Ali Ibrahim, Information Technology E-Service Management System, International Scientific Global Journal in Engineering Science and Applied Research (ISGJESAR). Vol.1. Issue 4, pp. 13-18, 2017. <http://isgjesar.com/Papers/Volume1,Issue4/paper2.pdf>
- [24] Ibrahim, Mr S. Jafar Ali, K. Singaraj, P. Jebaroopan, and S. A. Sheikfareed. "Android Based Robot for Industrial Application." *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology* 3, no. 3 (2014).
- [25] Ibrahim, S. Jafar Ali, and M. Thangamani. "Momentous Innovations in the Prospective Method of Drug Development."

- In Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Digital Medicine and Image Processing, pp. 37-41. 2018.
- [26] Ibrahim, S. Jafar Ali, and M. Thangamani. "Prediction of Novel Drugs and Diseases for Hepatocellular Carcinoma Based on Multi-Source Simulated Annealing Based Random Walk." *Journal of medical systems* 42, no. 10 (2018): 188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-018-1038-y>ISSN 1311-8080, <https://acadpubl.eu/hub/2018-119-16/1/94.pdf>
- [27] Jafar Ali Ibrahim. S, Mohamed Affir. A "Effective Scheduling of Jobs Using Reallocation of Resources Along With Best Fit Strategy and Priority", *International Journal of Science Engineering and Advanced Technology(IJSEAT)* – ISSN No: 2321- 6905, Vol.2, Issue.2, Feb-2014, <http://www.ijseat.com/index.php/ijseat/article/view/62>
- [28] M. Thangamani, and Jafar Ali Ibrahim. S, "Knowledge Exploration in Image Text Data using Data Hiding Scheme," *Lecture Notes in Engineering and Computer Science: Proceedings of The International MultiConference of Engineers and Computer Scientists 2018*, 14-16 March, 2018, Hong Kong, pp352-357http://www.iaeng.org/publication/IMECS2018/IMECS2018_pp352-357.pdf
- [29] M. Thangamani, and Jafar Ali Ibrahim. S, "Knowledge Exploration in Image Text Data using Data Hiding Scheme," *Lecture Notes in Engineering and Computer Science: Proceedings of The International MultiConference of Engineers and Computer Scientists 2018*, 14-16 March, 2018, Hong Kong, pp352-357http://www.iaeng.org/publication/IMECS2018/IMECS2018_pp352-357.pdf
- [30] S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim and M. Thangamani. 2018. Momentous Innovations in the Prospective Method of Drug Development. In *Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Digital Medicine and Image Processing (DMIP'18)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3299852.3299854>
- [31] S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim and Thangamani, M "Proliferators and Inhibitors Of Hepatocellular Carcinoma", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics (IJPAM) Special Issue of Mathematical Modelling of Engineering Problems* Vol 119 Issue. 15. July 2018
- [32] Thangamani, M., and S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim. "Ensemble Based Fuzzy with Particle Swarm Optimization Based Weighted Clustering (Efpsowc) and Gene Ontology for Microarray Gene Expression." In *Proceedings of the 2018 International Conference on Digital Medicine and Image Processing*, pp. 48-55. 2018. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3299852.3299866>
- [33] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar (2017) "Reliability Assessment of Component Based Software Systems using Basis Path Testing", *IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems, ICICCS 2017*, 512 – 517
- [34] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar(2017) ,"Construction of Estimated Level Based Balanced Binary Search Tree", 2017 *IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Communication, and Aerospace Technology (ICECA 2017)*, 344 - 348, 978-1-5090-5686-6.
- [35] R.Chinnaiyan, S.Somasundaram (2012) , Reliability Estimation Model for Software Components using CEP", *International Journal of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering (IJMIE)* , ISSN No.2231-6477, Volume-2, Issue-2, 2012, pp.89-93.
- [36] R.Chinnaiyan, S. Somasundaram (2011) ,"An SMS based Failure Maintenance and Reliability Management of Component Based Software Systems", *European Journal of Scientific Research*, Vol. 59 Issue 1, 9/1/2011, pp.123 (cited in EBSCO, Impact Factor: 0.045)
- [37] R.Chinnaiyan, S.Somasundaram(2011), "An Experimental Study on Reliability Estimation of GNU Compiler Components - A Review", *International Journal of Computer Applications*, Vol.25, No.3, July 2011, pp.13-16. (Impact Factor: 0.814)
- [38] R.Chinnaiyan, S.Somasundaram(2010) "Evaluating the Reliability of Component Based Software Systems " ,*International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management* , Vol. 27, No. 1., pp. 78-88 (Impact Factor: 0.406)
- [39] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar(2017), Estimation of Optimal Path in Wireless Sensor Networks based on Adjancy List, 2017 *IEEE International Conference on Telecommunication, Power Analysis and Computing Techniques (ICTPACT2017)* ,6,7,8th April 2017, IEEE 978-1-5090-3381-2.
- [40] Ibrahim, S. Jafar Ali, and M. Thangamani. "Enhanced singular value decomposition for prediction of drugs and diseases with hepatocellular carcinoma based on multi-source bat algorithm based random walk." *Measurement* 141 (2019): 176-183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2019.02.056>
- [41] Compound feature generation and boosting model for cancer gene classification Ibrahim, S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim., Affir, A.M., Thangamani, M. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 2020, 68(10), pp. 48–51, Doi No:doi:10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V68I10P208 <https://ijettjournal.org/Volume-68/Issue-10/IJETT-V68I10P208.pdf>
- [42] Innovative drug and disease prediction with dimensionality reduction and intelligence based random walk methods, Ibrahim, S.J.A., Thangamani, M. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, 2019, 8(4), pp. 1668–1673, <https://www.warse.org/IJATCSE/static/pdf/file/ijatcse93842019.pdf>
- [43] R. Ganesan, M. Thangamani, S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim, "Recent Research Trends and Advancements in Computational Linguistics", *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation* Vol 24, no 8 (2020):1154-1162, DOI: [10.37200/IJPR/V24I8/PR280128](https://doi.org/10.37200/IJPR/V24I8/PR280128)
- [44] C. Narmatha , Dr. M. Thangamani , S. Jafar Ali Ibrahim, " Research Scenario of Medical Data Mining Using Fuzzy and Graph theory", *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering*, Vol 9, No 1 (2020): 349-355
- [45] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan , R.Divya (2018), " Reliable AIBasedSmartSensorsforManagingIrrigationResources in Agriculture" , *Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, Springer International conference on Computer Networks and Inventive Communication Technologies (ICCNCT-2018)*, August 2018
- [46] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, S. Balachandrar(2018), "Reliable Digital Twin for Connected Footballer" , *Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, Springer International conference on Computer Networks and Inventive*

- eCommunication Technologies (ICCNCT- 2018), August 2018
- [47] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, S.Balachandar (2018), "Centralized Reliability and Security Management of Data in Internet of Things (IoT) with Rule Builder" Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, Springer International conference on Computer Networks and Inventive Communication Technologies (ICCNCT- 2018), August 2018 (Online)
- [48] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar (2017) "Reliability Assessment of Component Based Software Systems using Basis Path Testing", IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems, ICICCS 2017, 512 - 517
- [49] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar (2017), "Construction of Estimated Level Based Balanced Binary Search Tree", 2017 IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Communication, and Aerospace Technology (ICECA 2017), 344 - 348, 978-1-5090-5686-6.
- [50] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Abishek Kumar (2017), Estimation of Optimal Path in Wireless Sensor Networks based on Adjacency List, 2017 IEEE International Conference on Telecommunication, Power Analysis and Computing Techniques (ICTPACT 2017), 6, 7, 8th April 2017, IEEE 978-1-5090-3381-2.
- [51] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, R.Divya (2017), "Reliability Evaluation of Wireless Sensor Networks", IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems, ICICCS 2017, 847 - 852
- [52] Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Sabarmathi.G (2017), "Investigation on Big Data Features, Research Challenges and Applications", IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems, ICICCS 2017, 782 - 786
- [53] G.Sabarmathi, Dr.R.Chinnaiyan (2018), "Envisagation and Analysis of Mosquito Borne Fevers A Health Monitoring System by Envisagative Computing using Big Data Analytics" in ICCBI 2018 - Springer on 19.12.2018 to 20.12.2018 (Recommended for Scopus Indexed Publication IEEE Xplore digital library)
- [54] G.Sabarmathi, Dr.R.Chinnaiyan, Reliable Data Mining Tasks and Techniques for Industrial Applications, IAETSD JOURNAL FOR ADVANCED RESEARCH IN APPLIED SCIENCES, VOLUME 4, ISSUE 7, DEC/2017, PP-138-142, ISSN NO: 2394-8442